

The Memory of Asian-African Conference as a Public Diplomacy

Yudha Aditya Pratama¹, Junita Budi Rachman², Akim³

^{1,2,3} Padjadjaran University, Bandung, Indonesia.

ABSTRACT: This paper aims to explain the process of public diplomacy carried out by the Museum of the Asian-African Conference. This paper focuses on the role of museums as actors of public diplomacy that can help countries fulfill their national interests. This paper also explains what activities have been carried out by the museum to fulfill its role as an actor in Indonesian public diplomacy. The Museum of the Asian-African Conference itself is a historical museum that holds important memories about the Asian-African Conference. This study used qualitative paper methods. The data sources used in this study consist of two types, namely primary data sources such as data resulting from observations and interviews at the research location, while the secondary data itself is data obtained through literature study from articles related to the Museum of the Asian-African Conference such as books, journals, and electronic news. The data analysis process from this study includes five stages, namely data collection, data sorting, re-collection, data interpretation, and the conclusion. The results of this paper is about the museum's successes in carrying out Indonesian public diplomacy through events that organized by the museum. These activities also create opportunities for the Indonesian government to use them as a key for foreign policy making process.

KEYWORDS: asian-african conference, collective memory, museum of asian-african conference, public diplomacy.

INTRODUCTION

In a global world, every country has strategies to establish relations with one another. This strategy is divided into two, hard power and soft power. Hard power is an interaction carried out by a country through a traditional approach, namely by threatening, coercing, and undermining the power of other countries so that they submit to countries that have greater military power than other countries. The results of this strategy can be felt directly when the country succeeds in destroying the strength of the opposing country. Even so, the consequences of this strategy are fatal because it can trigger war on a larger scale. On the other hand, Soft power is an interaction carried out by a country by promoting peace and cooperation. This strategy can be carried out by all countries because it does not depend on the military strength of that country. The results of this strategy cannot be felt instantly but gradually over a long period of time. This strategy has a lower risk so it is very suitable for use by countries in the world to maintain peace.

Nye (2008) soft power is "the ability to influence the behavior of others to get the outcomes one wants". This strategy is the best way to achieve national interests without sacrificing the country's resources from war. Nye also emphasized that soft power is "the ability to get what you want through attraction rather than through coercion or payment". Countries can use culture, values, policies, and political institutions as tools of attraction in this strategy (Nye, 2008). Fukushima (2004) to achieve its national interests, the state can use its economic and cultural power. It can be used to carry out cooperation between countries. So war is not the only way to get what the country wants, but the path of peace can still be carried out through this strategy (Sasaki, 2006).

This paper explained soft power strategy through the public diplomacy method. Public diplomacy itself is a new method of diplomacy involving actors other than the state actor. This method aims foreign communities through cultural and economic approaches. By influencing foreign public opinion, the state will receive agents who support their foreign policy (Hennida, 2018).

The research object chosen in this study is the Museum of the Asian-African Conference. Unlike the other museums, this museum is a technical implementation unit of the ministry of foreign affairs (Primasanto, 2020). They maintains one of the most precious memories for countries in Asia and Africa. The memory is the event of the Asian-African Conference (AAC) on 18-25 April 1955. Located on Asian-African Street no. 65 Bandung West Java, making this museum have an easy access for local and international tourists. This museum was founded as a suggestion from Prof. Mochtar Kusumaatmadja as Minister of Foreign Affairs for the period 1978 – 1988, and was inaugurated on April 24, 1980 by President Soeharto. This museum operates every Tuesday - Sunday from 08.00 - 16.00, but specifically on Friday the museum is open from 14.00 - 16.00 (MAAC, 2019).

This study analyzes how museum carry out their public diplomacy process by utilizing the memories they maintain for the benefit of the state in international relations. Unfortunately that Indonesian government is still not aware that the process carried out by this museum can open up many factors that will support the establishment of new cooperation between countries.

METHODS

This research uses qualitative methods. Yin (2011) the qualitative method is a research method that focuses on processing data from a series of phenomena that occur at the research location. The research technique used was field observation, collecting articles and related data, as well as interviewing the museum manager. The data collection process was conducted for 6 months in two sessions. The first session in on May - August 2019 and the second session held in July - August 2020. The data collection process was disturbed by the covid-19 pandemic and was resumed when the museum resumed its operations.

The field observation process carried out included collecting data at the museum of the Asian-African Conference such as museum information, history of the Asian-African Conference, stored collections, as well as the activities of visitors and museum observer groups namely Friends of the Museum of the Asian-African Conference. Meanwhile the interview process in this study aims to collect more in-depth information about museum activities, museum relations with foreign ministries, and matching data that occurs in the museum with the theory used. The resource person who assisted in the data collection process was the head of the sustainability and public diplomacy documentation section. Five steps to analyzing the data through this research method, which include compile database, disassembling data, reassembling data, interpreting data, and conclusion (Yin, 2011).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

I. Museum of Asian-African Conference''[[

The Museum of the Asian-African Conference is a museum managed by the government. In the organization hierarchy, the Directorate General of Information and Public Diplomacy took a role as echelon one, the Directorate of Public Diplomacy as echelon two, and the Museum of the Asian-African Conference as echelon three. The staff managing the museum are employees of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. Therefore all museum staff also have the same logo, email domain, employee identification card, ID card, attendance sheet, and payroll system as the central Ministry of Foreign Affairs in Jakarta. This can be seen from the uniforms used by the security officers who stand guard outside where they have the words "KEMLU" on the back of their uniforms (Primasanto, 2020).

This museum is categorized as a history museum. The types of items displayed by the museum include pictures, photographs, and dioramas. These items describe how the Asian African Conference took place. That way visitors can observe and learn about the history of AAC directly at the museum location (Seki, 2014). This museum provides several interesting facilities for visitors. Some of the facilities provided by the Museum include displays of museum collections, a library, stands for souvenirs, as well as special facilities provided to visitors who want to do research. Therefore this museum can also meet the requirements of the benefits of the museum itself, namely as an educational, innovative, recreational and imaginative means (Suratmin, 2019).

In its operational process, the museum also forms a community that can lighten the burden on the museum in carrying out its activities. The community is named Friends of the Museum of the Asian-African Conference. The background for the establishment of this community was the large number of people who liked to gather around the museum in 2008. They wanted a space where they could do positive and useful things. Therefore, the museum confirmed them as Friends of the Museum of the Asian-African Conference in 2011.

II. Implementation of Three Dimension Of Public Diplomacy

Public diplomacy relations will work well if they are carried out properly and sustainably for a long time. To achieve this, public diplomats must implement three important dimensions in public diplomacy, namely short, medium and long dimensions. (Short dimension) is daily communication which concerns domestic issues and the establishment of foreign policy, (Medium dimension) is strategic communication which concerns the development of diplomatic themes as a political tool or as a tool for disseminating the diplomatic theme, (Long dimension) is the development of relations long-term relationships with targeted individuals through scholarships, student exchanges, training, seminars, conferences, and the provision of media channels (Nye, 2008).

a) Short Dimension

Museum of the Asian-African Conference has a Standard Operating Procedure that has been approved by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. This procedure was used as a guide in the museum's managerial processes. The matters regulated in this procedure include reservations, arrangements for issued information, security arrangements, and services to museum visitors

The Museum of the Asian-African Conference explains that daily communication was indeed carried out by the museum, and among them were several activities related to the procedure owned by the Museum itself.

The activities discussed by the Museum include the following:

1) Establishment of policies about information that released to the media and the press

The Museum has made a policy to process information that will be submitted to the press accordance with the wishes of the head of the museum and has been approved by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. This is done to avoid any miscommunication between the central unit (Ministry of Foreign Affairs) and the field implementation unit (Museum of the Asian-African Conference).

The information that will be released by the museum was divided into two types, direct information and published information. Direct information is information that will be conveyed directly by the museum to those who need it, including researchers and the press. In carrying out this activity, the museum must make several preparations in advance and consult with the central unit in choosing words and information to convey. When the request issued by a party requiring information is not in accordance with the wishes or ability of the Museum to provide information, the museum will take steps to direct this party to a more appropriate agency or place for the process of extracting the information. The museum also has the authority to refuse to provide information if the party that requires information that is inappropriate or sensitive information is beyond the authority of the museum. The press in the process of public diplomacy can be a double-edged sword if not managed carefully. This can be found when America failed to manage the information that came out to the Middle Eastern media which resulted in the failure of public diplomacy in the Middle East at that time. Therefore, the relationship between the press and public diplomats must be managed in as much detail as possible to manage these foreign resources as a way of shaping international politics (Zhang, 2021). Meanwhile, the information that will be published is information that will usually be published on information channels owned by the Museum such as Social Media and Websites. This information contains the history of the Asian-African Conference, activities carried out by the Museum, as well as other information obtained from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. This type of information can be easily accessed by visiting the museum's social media or its website. This method will increase the dissemination of information. Online users often send the information they get on their social media accounts to their family, office friends, or social media friends.

2) Establishment of policies about security protocols

In terms of security, the museum has used a fairly good security protocol. This was intended to maintain the security of visitors, staff, and collections of artifact owned by the museum. Some examples of security protocols carried are guarding by security forces at all entrances, providing metal detectors to avoid criminal activities, recording detailed visitor data, and securing special guests.

When the pandemic occurred, the museum implemented the health protocol recommended by the ministry of health and the local government. This is the initial step taken by the museum to maintain the safety of visitors, staff, and museum collections from contamination by the COVID-19 virus. The museum's fulfillment of health protocols includes checking body temperature, applying mandatory masks for visitors, giving hand sanitizers, and maintaining distance in the process of visiting the museum. The implementation of this health protocol lasted for several days until finally the museum decided to close as part of fulfilling the obligations from the regional government in the PSBB program.

3) Establishment of policies in the operational schedule of the museum when facing extraordinary situations

When facing extraordinary situations, Museum may also change its hours of operation according to local regulations. In general, museums also close museums on major national holidays. However, the museum will also close public access when facing extraordinary situations such as visits from VVIP guests, organizing events, or pandemic situations. Some examples of cases include the closing of the museum during the celebration of the 2019 Asia Africa Festival event on 29 June 2019, the visit of the President of Namibia Dr. Hage Gottfried Geingob on 31 August 2018 (MAAC, 2018), and the closing of the museum during the COVID-19 pandemic on 15 March 2020. This regulation occurred not only for museum activities but also to maintain the safety of museum visitors.

b) Medium Dimension

Strategic communication was also carried out by the museum as a fulfillment of its duties as the Technical Implementation Unit of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. Museum does not want to be a collections room but also want to become an information medium that is inclusive and open to anyone. Therefore museum always tries to carry out various kinds of activities that involve young people, people with disabilities, the general public, and even foreigners such as foreign visitors or foreign students studying in Indonesia. To achieve this, museum uses all lines in the information dissemination process such as posters, newspapers, electronic news, social media, as well as Friends of the Museum of the Asian-African Conference.

The Museum of the Asian-African Conference also has other ways to attract visitors to come and enjoy the attraction. The method used by the museum is creating an event that is very interesting for the public to follow. The Events can be divided into two parts, such as big events and normal events.

1) Big Event

The Big Event is one of the major events from the Museum of the Asian-African Conference. This event is usually held once a year. This event is held to commemorate the anniversary of the Asian-African Conference on April 24 each year. This event is not only the pride of the museum but is also recognized by the local and central government as a very important event. People from various regions and foreign countries participate in this activity, which makes this event one of the most spectacular activities and attracts the public's interest to watch it.

This event aims to develop the theme of public diplomacy. By holding this event, the museum can campaign for the Asian-African Conference to the public in very large numbers. This event is usually not only attended by local people, but also by people from foreign countries. This event is also used as a point of success for Indonesia along with Asian-African countries to commemorate the success of the Asian-African Conference.

This event is called Asia Africa Festival. It is a celebration to commemorate the anniversary of the Asian-African Conference and to promote the cultures of the participating countries. The Asia Africa Festival is held once a year, and each year it always attracts tourists who watch in large numbers. This event was started in 2005 to commemorate the 50th anniversary of the Asian-African Conference. Since then, the Asia-Africa Festival has been held once a year. However, since 2012 the Museum has begun to reduce its full involvement in matters of a Festivities nature, so that the Asia-African Festival is largely handed over to the regional government. The events that are being prioritized by the Museum of the Asian-African Conference are educational. Even though the role of the museum in organizing the Asia Africa Festival is no longer full, the museum still take a part in terms of providing substance and connections with the diplomatic corps that invited to the Asia Africa Festival.

The most recent Asia Africa Festival was held in 2019. The Asia Africa Festival 2019 was held on June 29 2019. Unfortunately from 2020 to 2022, the Asia Africa Festival could not be held. The status of the City of Bandung is currently on lockdown where the location of this event and the museum location are closed, so this year's event cannot be held. Besides that, the cancellation of this event was also to avoid crowds that could become the center of the spreading the COVID-19 virus. But it is hoped in 2023 this big event can be held again as usual.

2) Normal Event

The normal event is one of the activities carried out by the Museum to attract visitors on certain occasions. This event is usually held to commemorate national holidays or the result of collaboration with other parties. This event held as an effort to attract people to visit the Museum. And also be used to increase the popularity of museums as entertainment and educational facilities for the community.

This normal event focuses more on educational events, where event participants will be presented with substances about the history of the Asian-African Conference that are packaged in a unique, creative and fun way.

The following are some examples of normal events carried out by the Museum of the Asian-African Conference.

- 1) Bandung Historical Study Game (BHS): An activity that combines walking and learning history. Participants are required to complete challenges that contain information and history regarding the Asian-African Conference in each post. Recently, the museum held BHS 2022 with the theme Recover Together, Recover Stronger. By using the virtual method, BHS 2022 has succeeded in attracting a lot of interest from students with the tagline Think Globally, Act Locally. In BSHG's speech, the head of the museum said that in the future BSHG would become one of the main programs for the museum (Septiani, 2022).

- 2) Night Museum Exploration: an event that held on national holidays. Participants come wearing predetermined costumes while exploring the museum and completing the challenges. After a hiatus for two years, the Night Museum Exploration was held again. Night Museum Exploration with the theme Sutan Sjahrir: Architect of Struggle Diplomacy which was attended by more than 350 participants with 15-20 people in each group (Salman, 2022).
- 3) Hitchcock's Movies Screenings & Talks: the result of a collaboration between the Museum of the Asian-African Conference with the Institut Francais d'Indonesia Bandung and the LayarKita Community. This event takes place from February 1 to February 29 2016. In this event, visitors will be presented with screenings of Alfred Hitchcock's films (MAAC, 2016).

c) Long Dimension

The Museum of the Asian-African Conference realizes that strategy in establishing long-term relations is one of the main factors in the sustainability of the process of public diplomacy that they carry out. Some activities that can be categorized as long-term communication are as follows.

- 1) The museum oversees the process of providing scholarships for foreign students studying in Indonesia, especially those from Asian and African countries.
The students who are supervised and guided by the Museum of the Asian-African Conference are grouped into two major groups namely the Young African Ambassadors in Asia (YAAA) and the Asian Student Association in Indonesia (ASAI). YAAA is an association of foreign students from African countries who are currently studying at several universities in Indonesia. At the end of 2014, the Museum gave a warm welcome to the students who were selected for this scholarship program. The museum also includes YAAA as part of the museum family which is incorporated into the "Young African Ambassadors in Asia Club" in the Friends of the Museum of the Asian-African Conference. Meanwhile, ASAI is an association of foreign students from Asian countries. The museum also includes ASAI in the museum family which is incorporated into the "Asian Student Association in Indonesia Club" within the Friends of the Museum of the Asia-Africa Conference. The museum takes an approach by inviting them to various activities organized by the museum and teaching the values of the Asian-African Conference in them. So that these students can become agents of public diplomacy for Indonesia, which not only promotes the Asian African Spirit but also promotes Indonesia to their country of origin (MKAA, 2014).
- 2) The Museum held a conference called the Asian-African Student Conference (AASC) in 2015.
The conference was attended by students from Asian-African countries as representatives of the young Asian-African generation. This conference raised issues that were being faced by Asian African students at that time. The issues raised are issues of inclusive education, the media as a pillar of the democratic process, open sources for digital independence, strategies for encouraging leadership to promote Asian-African cultural values, as well as a global network of Asian-African students. From the conference, four points were agreed upon by all the students involved, namely: Strengthening the resolution of the 1955 Asian-African Conference and voicing to all students that the spirit of Bandung can be used as a basis for collaboration ; Providing recommendations regarding the implementation of the declaration of human rights in the Asian and African regions, opposing and punishing colonialism, and setting April 18 as Asia-Africa anti-colonialism day; Support the struggle of the Algerian people, the people of Kenya, the people of Palestine, and the restoration of the rights of Arab refugees to return to their respective countries; As well as encouraging students to be active in nation-building according to the function of the intelligentsia in society (Atmosuwito, 2015).
- 3) The museum held a monthly seminar called Update from Foreign Ministry.
This seminar is open to the public so that does not rule out the possibility that participants from this seminar are not only local people such students and local participant but also come from outside ring such as foreign students. This seminar discussed the update of foreign policy programs carried out by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs.
- 4) The museum also provides access to media channels for the public.
The Museum provides several media channels, including the official website of the Museum and the Museum's official social media such as Facebook, Twitter, Youtube, and Instagram. This makes the information provided by the museum accessible to anyone anywhere and anytime. These channels contain information about museums, the history of the Asian-African Conference, the latest updates on activities carried out by the museum, and further information from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. Yasserri

(2022) the availability of social media platforms has changed the accessibility of historical data which was previously limited to political elites, families of war victims, and veterans to become open for everyone who is connected in a globalized world. Therefore, the museum's step in improving media access to be more up-to-date is the best thing to keep up with the times. The emergence of the Covid-19 pandemic requires museums to be able to take advantage of social media to cover limitations during a pandemic such as organizing online seminars, online agendas, and launching online-based features. A new feature has been launched to overcome limitations during a pandemic where visitors cannot visit the museum, this feature is called the Museum of the Asian-African Conference Virtual Tour. With the many access that the museum has provided, it can be useful not only in public diplomacy but also in journalism, media development, policy making, and advertising (Yasseri, 2022)

III. Protected Memories in The Museum

The Museum of the Asian-African Conference is categorized into types of historical museums. Therefore the type of object sold to visitors is a memory. Heersmink (2021) memory can be characterized as a cultural memory if it has been formally established and used as historical knowledge in the form of artifacts, teaching, and expert understanding (Heersmink, 2021). The memory that we talked about is the Asian-African Conference, it was the starting point for forming a bond of friendship between Asian-African countries to create a global movement, namely the Non-Aligned Movement (NAM). The events displayed by the museum are packaged into various forms, from photos, infographics, dioramas, audiovisuals, and relics, as well as the place where this history was hapened, namely Gedung Merdeka. The artifacts stored here can be categorized as cultural artifacts. This is because the artifacts on display have high historical value so that they can help visitors remember past events regarding the Asian-African Conference (Heersmink, 2021).

The memory protected by the Museum is a positive memory that contains the journeys of Asian and African countries in determining their existence in the international world. This memory is one of the tools used by Asian and African countries to strengthen solidarity between nations (Zubrzycki, 2020). During the cold war, these countries were very vulnerable to attacks from the influence of the superpowers, but with strong solidarity, these countries united to reject western colonialism during the cold war. This memory is a form of collective memory shared by Asian and African countries. Gagnepain (2019) collective memory is a collection of memories from individuals or representatives that emerged from an event that everyone felt (Gagnepain, 2019). Collective memory itself consists of several types which include folk memory, commemorative memory, and mediatised memory. Folk memory is a memory that spread among several individuals regarding daily activities which gradually turns into a community tradition, commemorative memory is a memory obtained by individuals during an event that has special uses such as a public celebration that begins with a statement and ended by the establishment of a monument as a place to store the memory, and mediatised memory is a record of the past which is consumed as part of entertainment for the community. The memory of the Asia-Africa Conference is included in commemorative memory because it was created from the results of organizing a celebration that began with making a statement and ended with the creation of a monument to save the memory. O'Connor (2019) commemorative memory is an instrument of individual and community hegemony because it has a big long-term impact such as increasing the spirit of patriotism and inspiration for generations to enjoy it in the future (O'Connor, 2019). Bachleitner (2021) after memory turns into part of a country's identity, it starts to affect the country's attitude toward the outside world, including the country's foreign policy. Therefore utilizing this memory will provide enormous benefits for Indonesia (Bachleitner, 2021).

This memory was presented in the form of photographs, dioramas, original items used at that time, as well as the location where the event took place. There are lots of photos describing the journey of the Asian-African Conference. Starting from the process of welcoming delegates from Asian-African countries who attended this conference, besides that there were also many photos of the process when the conference happened and the photos of the excitement that occurred around the location of the building at that time. These photos are also equipped with information that explains what the photos mean. The museum also has photos of figures who played an important role in the implementation of this conference.

Besides photos, there are also lots of infographics that contain various kinds of information. Starting from information about the cold war, the second world war, the issue of apartheid, the issue of colonialism, as well as the conditions of Asian and African countries before this conference was held. This is intended so that visitors can understand the situation that was happening at the time this conference was held. The museum also displays a fragment of newspapers from around the world highlighting the Asian-African Conference. There is one collection that can be used as a source of memory from Asian and African countries, namely a copy of the

"Dasa Sila Bandung". It contained ten principle about human rights, national integrity, respect, neutrality, non violence, peace keeping, developing all member interest, and cooperations.

Another collection on display at the museum is a historical relic that witnessed the Asian-African Conference taking place. there are several collections such as rattan chairs and tables used in the process of formulating the Dasa Sila Bandung at the Asian-African Conference. The museum also displays the typewriter and telex that were used when the conference happened. Then there is an enlarger that functions to print the photos that were captured at the conference. The museum also managed to save the postal scales and postmarks used at the conference. The museum also exhibits special postage stamps depicting the Asian-African Conference in 1955, which is a favorite location for stamp enthusiasts. The Asia Africa Museum also has vinyl records of President Soekarno's speech at this conference as well as a diorama depicting President Soekarno while making his speech on the podium in front of five representatives of the sponsoring countries who were sitting behind President Soekarno.

Meanwhile, the main collection which is the icon of this museum is the main exhibition of Gedung Merdeka. This building itself was the venue for the Asian-African Conference in 1955. The building has a high historical value because the placement of the items inside are still authentic to the items used at the time when the conference took place. Only a few things have been changed for maintenance purposes such as seat foam to make it more durable. Inside the main room, there is also the Gong of Peace where this gong depicts the strong attachment of Asian and African countries to one another. This gong contains the flags and symbols of all the countries participating in the Asian-African Conference (TVBinus, 2018).

IV. Public Diplomacy of Museum of Asian-African Conference

Based on obtained data, museum already have sufficient competence to carry out the process of public diplomacy even though it is slightly different from diplomatic actors in general. This museum itself has a function besides being able to preserve cultural heritage in the form of memory of the Asian-African Conference, this museum has also succeeded in carrying out its duties as technical implementation unit of the ministry of foreign affairs. Zhang (2021) public diplomacy is a communication with foreign publics to influence the way of thinking and attitudes of the people and influence the foreign policies of other countries (Zhang, 2021). Even though the museum is not located outside Indonesia, its influence on the foreign public is quite strong because the scope of visitors and the target of the museum itself are not only local visitors but also foreign visitors, foreign press, students, and foreign government officials. Therefore, the role of the museum as an actor in Indonesia's public diplomacy has succeeded in improving the country's image well. With many state visits by both ambassadors and heads of state, the spirit of Bandung contained in the Dasa Sila Bandung will bring back memories of the glory of Asian and African countries in the past as pillars of friendship between countries.

At the celebration of the Asia Africa Festival, Indonesia promotes local culture to invited guests and also visitors who attend. This can promote local culture to the international realm. The culture displayed at this festival is not only music and dance but also handicrafts and food. The surrounding community who take part in this celebration will benefit financially as well as the government in improving its image. Meanwhile, for educational-themed events, the museum has also managed to spread its influence through students participating in activities such as BHSG and Night Museum Exploration. The students became very enthusiastic in participating in these events because they were fun and rich of information and history about AAC. Besides challenge the participants to solve puzzles and questions, the participants were also brought to reminisce in the nuances of the city of Bandung in the AAC era. This memory must be maintained, especially by the younger generation so that the glory of this memory does not fade away. Goldsmith (2021) to increase the strength of its soft power, state must be able to use important tools in public diplomacy activities such as government foreign broadcasts and cultural events. This aims to provide an opportunity for foreign governments to come and visit the host country. Often events like this are one of the main reasons for the leaders of countries to travel internationally. It is hoped that this visit will strengthen relations between countries and improve the country's image internationally when the press covers this matter in the news (Goldsmith, 2021).

Another success was the birth of Indonesian agents through YAAA and ASAI which were directly supervised by the museum. By joining them in the museum family, the distribution of museum influences to Asian and African countries will be easier and more focused. When these students have completed their education and return to their home countries, it is hoped that they will become agents of Indonesian public diplomacy in the future. Other activities such as the Asian-African student conference also play a very important role for the younger generation, because they are faced with the problems that are currently happening in Asia and Africa. They are required to be able to understand, study, and establish an agreement to resolve these problems as part of solidarity between

members of Asian and African countries. This activity will certainly encourage students to be able to realize the decisions they make someday. Mulvey (2019) the expected result of public diplomacy through the provision of scholarships for foreign students is to develop student opinion towards the provider country so that it can improve relations between the student country and the country providing scholarship. In other words, the process of awarding scholarships to foreign students is a tool of diplomacy while the positive opinion of the students is a proxy for soft power. Wilson (2017) the benefits of the positive opinions of these students will multiply when these alumni begin to enter into position of power in their home countries such as working as government employees or moving as agents who can influence public opinion such as journalists and teaching staff. The advantages that Indonesia has compared to other countries can be seen in the case of China. It was noted that the efficiency of the Chinese scholarship program for African countries was hampered by several factors such as very high racism to the lack of use of international languages in the process. This has resulted in some African students feeling alienated and not associating with the surrounding area, making it difficult to generate positive opinions from students towards the host country. Unlike the program carried out by Indonesia where YAAA and ASAI themselves are included as a big family in the Friends of the Museum of the Asian-African Conference, the spirit of Asia-Africa eliminates racism and international language barriers that students complain about in the case of Chinese scholarships (Mulvey, 2019).

The update from foreign ministry program is also an effective way of spreading information to the public about the direction of the Indonesian foreign ministry's policies. Often this activity is used by students to obtain information about policies that have been and will be implemented by the ministry of foreign affairs. Other parties who often use this activity are news journalists and also members of foreign embassies as part of their work.

The emergence of a pandemic also made it difficult for museums to carry out their activities. The lockdown that was carried out by Indonesia some time ago caused the museum to also close and cancel its routine agenda. Therefore, museums try to maximize electronic media as a way to overcome their limitations during a pandemic. This is getting satisfactory results because lately the younger generation is often dependent on social media. Therefore, to take advantage of this, an online-based agenda is created, such as online seminars, live broadcasts, and the launch of the Museum of the Asian-African Conference Virtual Tour.

To maximize its public diplomacy process, Indonesia must be able to take advantage of the opportunities that arise in every activity that has been carried out by the museum. This opportunity can be used by the government as one of the factors in the formulation of cooperation between countries. Several opportunities that can be utilized by the government include the Asia Africa Festival, BHSG, Night Museum Exploration, Asian African student conference, as well as utilization of museum resources namely YAAA and ASAI as agents of public diplomacy that can assist the Indonesian government in spreading the spirit of Asia and Africa in their home country.

Asia Africa Festival is one of the great opportunities to help Indonesia in starting communication between countries. This annual festival is often attended by delegates from Asian and African countries. The memory of the glory of Asian and African countries will strengthen the friendship of these countries which is expected to bring up an agenda to develop existing cooperation or create new cooperation that is mutually beneficial to one another. 2023 is the best year to hold this festival again, where the excitement that has been lost in the last two years is the most awaited moment by the public.

Collaboration can also be carried out between state governments such as the provision of foreign scholarships for students which can be used as the main prize for organizing this event. So, the enthusiasm of students to take part in this event will increase significantly. The collaboration between museums and Asian and African countries in creating new events will also be very beneficial for the Indonesian government. When this happens, the relationship between the Indonesian government and Asian and African countries will improve, followed by an increase in public satisfaction and the spread of Asian and African values in society. Krasnyak (2019) in the process of increasing soft power in public diplomacy, countries can use their foreign policy campaigns regarding geopolitical interests. New events that can be held in 2023 can start with cooperation events with countries in Southeast Asia (Krasnyak, 2019). This can help Indonesia spread the spirit of Asia and Africa and fulfill the direction of Indonesia's diplomacy in 2023 (Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2023).

CONCLUSION AND SUGESTION

Based on the results obtained from this study, the museum of the Asian-African Conference has succeeded in implementing Indonesian public diplomacy by following the three dimensions of public diplomacy as a guideline. The museum has also succeeded

in utilizing its memory in making events that will greatly assist the government in improving its image in the local and international public. However, due to a lack of literacy and information discussing this matter, the government was still unable to make full use of this activity.

After the world has recovered from the COVID-19 pandemic, various activities can return to normal. Therefore, the authors suggest the government to re-organize interesting events that will attract the interest of the younger generation to care about the important memories of their nation. The re-organization of the Asian African Student Conference will also improve the critical way of thinking of Asian and African students. As well as strengthening relations with YAAA and ASAI by carrying out joint events as part of the big family of Friends of the Museum of the Asian-African Conference.

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